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Review Article

Aspirin: A Review On Analytical Method Development And Validation For Tablet Dosage Form By UV Visible Spectroscopy

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ABSTRACT

Many topical anti-infective agents have been developed by conventional medicine; however, due to the emergence of antibiotic- and chemotherapeutic-resistant pathogens, some of these agents are no longer very effective. Ozone has been known for more than a century to be a great disinfectant, but because of its oxidizing qualities, it needed to be used carefully. Only in the past ten years has it been possible to permanently incorporate the gas into triglycerides, where gaseous ozone chemically reacts with unsaturated substrates to produce ozonated derivatives that are therapeutically active, thereby taming its extreme reactivity. As of right now, ozonated oils have proven to be stable and effective. However, because there are so many commercial products available, this paper will examine these derivatives and offer a method for producing the best products possible.

INTRODUCTION

Acetylsalicylic acid, the common name for aspirin, is a salicylate medication that is frequently used as an antipyretic, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory. It also inhibits the production of thromboxane, which normally binds platelets together to form a patch over blood vessel wall damage. This action causes an antiplatelet effect. In terms of chemistry, it is 2-acetoxybenzoic acid, which is classified as a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medication (NSAID) and exhibits suppression of the

cyclooxygenase enzyme. It is recognized in the British, Indian Pharmacopoeia. Literature survey revealed that there are various methods have been reported for estimation of ASP such as UV, HPLC, Fluorimetry individually and in combined dosage form with other drugs.

MOA

Prostaglandin production is inhibited by acetylsalicylic acid (ASA). For COX-1 and COX-2 enzymes 9, 10, 11, it is non-selective. The usual platelet lifespan is 7–10 days, during which time

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COX-1 inhibition prevents platelet aggregation. The cyclooxygenase-1 (COX-1) enzyme's serine residue binds to the acetyl group of acetylsalicylic acid, is not produced by this mechanism from arachidonic acid. The accumulation of platelets can cause blood clots and dangerous venous and arterial thromboembolism, which can result in illnesses like stroke and pulmonary embolism. By specifically targeting cyclooxygenase-1 (COX-1) and cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), acetylsalicylic acid interferes with the body's ability to produce prostaglandins. It has been demonstrated that injecting prostaglandins into humans can result in discomfort and headaches due to their strong and

acid, causing permanent inactivation. As a result, prostaglandins that cause pain are not produced. Additionally, thromboxane A2 (TXA2), a strong irritating nature. Bradykinin and histamine are two chemicals that are more sensitive to pain when prostaglandins are present. This medication may block prostaglandins from acting at pain receptors and preventing the release of prostaglandins in inflammation, hence preventing pain symptoms. Because it can prevent the brain's prostaglandin E1 from being produced, acetylsalicylic acid is regarded as an antipyretic. Prostaglandin E1 is well known for being a very potent fever-inducing substance.[16]

Fig.no. 1 MOA Aspirin

UV-Visible spectrophotometers

UV-Visible spectrophotometers provide quick and effective analysis in analytical chemistry. They require only little amounts of substances (at mg & µg levels), which are frequently recoverable after testing, and they provide permanent chart-recorded information. Because UV-visible

spectrophotometry is so sensitive and selective, it is useful for identifying substances in complicated combinations and finding minute contaminants. [42]

Analytical method validation

It is crucial for ensuring the efficacy and safety of medicinal products by assessing their overall

purity during storage, distribution, and use. Validated procedures establish the quality relationship between the examined substance and the one initially evaluated pharmaceutically, toxicologically, and pharmacologically. Sound quality control relies on validated analytical methods, essential for manufacturing, government control laboratories, or pharmacopoeia inclusion. Key validation characteristics include specificity, linearity, range, accuracy, precision, detection limit, quantitation limit, and robustness. These parameters ensure that the analytical method produces reliable data fit for its intended purpose. [44]

Suresh Kumar S et al

It has been designed and confirmed to analyze aspirin in the presence of its breakdown products using a High-Performance Liquid Chromatography approach that is sensitive, specific, precise, and economical. Hypersil BDS C18 (100 x 4.6 mm 5 μ) column was used as the stationary phase in this approach. In the mobile phase, there was isopropyl alcohol (85%:14:1% v/v), acetonitrile, and sodium perchlorate buffer (pH 2.5). A flow rate of 1.5 ml min⁻¹ is applied as it passes through the chromatographic apparatus. Around 275 nm, the UV detector is in use. Aspirin and its breakdown products were found to be well-resolved by this approach. According to ICH criteria, the method was validated.[1]

Kokot et al

Using "zero crossing" second-derivative UV spectrophotometry, a quick and easy assay method was created for the simultaneous measurement of aspirin (ASA) and salicylic acid (SA) in aspirin delayed-release tablet formulation. Acetonitrile±formic acid (99:1) was used as a diluting solution to record the zero-order absorption spectra and second derivative spectra of ASA and SA. The technique's correctness was shown by comparing the findings of the high-

performance liquid chromatographic method with the stated approach for determining the levels of ASA and SA in 20 tablets from the same batch. Both methods yielded good agreement. [2]

Franeta et al

A chromatographic system including a Bio Rad 18 01 solvent pump, Rheodine 71 25 injector, and Vis detector is used in the current HPLC approach to determine acetylsalicylic acid, paracetamol, caffeine, and phenobarbital in tablets simultaneously. A 5 mm, 250 / 4.6 mm Bio SiL HL C18 column was used to accomplish separation. 2.0 milliliters per minute of a 25:75 v/v acetonitrile and water mixture that had been pH-adjusted using phosphoric acid was utilized as the mobile phase. At 0.01 AUFS, the UV detection ranged to 207 nm. It was able to measure the amount of salicylic acid under the same circumstances. The selectivity factor, resolution factor, peak asymmetry, capacity factor, retention durations, and other chromatographic parameters were calculated. The validation parameters include intra-day and linearity ($r / 0.998$). The validation parameters that were found to be satisfactory were: linearity ($r / 0.998$), intra-day precision (RSD: 0.36 / 1.89%), inter-day precision (RSD: 0.58 / 2.18%), sensitivity (LOD: 9 / 10 5 / 1.7 / 10 4 mg ml 1 and LOQ: 2.5 / 10 4 / 5.6 / 10 4 mg ml 1), accuracy (recoveries: 98.35 / 99.14%), and reproducibility (recovery values: 98.74 / 102.08% for acetylsalicylic acid, 99.93 / 102.11% for paracetamol, 98.25 / 102.12% for caffeine, and 98.15 / 102.3% for phenobarbital) (RSD: 1.21 / 1.85%). Acetylsalicylic acid, caffeine, paracetamol, and phenobarbital have all been found in Malophenum tablets using the suggested HPLC approach. Within 0.99 / 1.21% of the obtained RSD values. Because of its speed and sensitivity, the new technology may be used to regularly monitor the dose form of these medications [3]

Eva-Luise Ritter-Hobl et al

For the purpose of simultaneously quantifying acetylsalicylic acid and its metabolite salicylic acid in human plasma, a high-performance liquid chromatography approach was devised that is selective, sensitive, fast, and incorporates post-column hydrolysis and fluorescence detection. The analytes were separated on a ProntoSIL120C18ace-EPS column (150 2mm, 3mm), shielded by a C8guard column (5mm), after the addition of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzoic acid as an internal standard and straightforward protein precipitation with acetonitrile. Using acetonitrile (70:30, v/v) and 10 mM formic acid in water (pH 2.9), the mobile phase was utilized at a flow rate of 0.35 mL/min. Following the addition of an alkaline solution to hydrolyze acetylsalicylic acid (ASA) to salicylic acid (SA) on-line, the analytes were detected at 290 nm (lex) and 400 nm (lem). The technique demonstrated linearity in the concentration ranges of 0.05 to 20 ng/mL for both ASA and SA, with a quantification lower limit of 25 pg/mL for SA and 50 pg/mL for ASA. 15 pg/mL for SA and 32.5 pg/mL for ASA was the limit of detection. This approach is appropriate for measuring plasma salicylate concentrations in clinical routines since it may be completed in 8 minutes for the measurement of ASA and SA. [4]

N Ramos-Martos

This paper describes a rapid reversed-phase liquid chromatographic method, with UV detection, for the simultaneous determination of acetylsalicylic acid, caffeine, codeine, paracetamol, pyridoxine, and thiamine in pharmaceutical preparations. A reversed-phase C18 Nucleosil column is used. The mobile phase consists of 2 successive eluants: water (5 min) and acetonitrile-water (75 + 25, v/v; 9 min), both adjusted to pH 2.1 with phosphoric acid. Before determination acetylsalicylic acid is completely converted to salicylic acid by alkaline hydrolysis. Salicylic acid, caffeine, paracetamol, pyridoxine, and thiamine are all detected at 285 nm, whereas codeine is detected at 240 nm.

Calibration curves were linear for salicylic acid, caffeine, paracetamol, and pyridoxine in the range of 50-500 mg/L, and for codeine and thiamine in the range of 50-1000 mg/L. The method was applied to the analysis of 13 fortified commercial pharmaceutical preparations. Recoveries ranged from 92.6 to 105.5%, with relative standard deviations of 1.1-5.8%. [5]

Dalibor Satínský et al

Based on a unique reversed-phase sequential injection chromatography (SIC) approach with UV detection, a new separation method was developed for the simultaneous determination of paracetamol, caffeine, acetylsalicylic acid, and internal standard benzoic acid. In this investigation, we employed an FIALab 3000 system (USA) with an 8-port selection valve and a 5 mL syringe for sequential injection chromatographic separations, together with a Chromolith Flash RP-18e, 25-4.6mm column (Merck, Germany). Acetonitrile-(0.01 M) phosphate buffer (10:90, v/v), pH 4.05, flow rate: 0.6 mL min⁻¹. This was the mobile phase that was employed. At 210 and 230 nm, UV was detected. The validation parameters yielded positive results: all compounds had linearity ($r > 0.999$); detection limits were within the range of 0.3-0.8 microg mL⁻¹; peak height repeatability (RSD) between runs was within the range of 1.10-4.30% at three concentration levels; and intra-day repeatability of retention times was within the range of 0.28-0.43%. About six minutes passed during the analysis. The technique proved useful for routinely analyzing the active ingredients in prescription tablets, such as acetylsalicylic acid, caffeine, and paracetamol.[6]

Kachave R et al

A reliable and precise RP-HPLC method was developed to simultaneously determine the amounts of Aspirin and Ticlopidine Hydrochloride in both their bulk form and tablet dosage form. The analysis was performed using an Inertsil ODS C18

column with a mobile phase consisting of 0.02M Potassium dihydrogen o-phosphate (pH 3.7) and Methanol at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. Detection was achieved at 254 nm, with retention times of 3.3 minutes for Aspirin and 7.3 minutes for Ticlopidine Hydrochloride. The calibration curves showed linearity over the concentration ranges of 16µg/mL to 24µg/mL for Aspirin and 40µg/mL to 60µg/mL for Ticlopidine Hydrochloride. The method exhibited good interday and intraday precision, and met the sensitivity, reproducibility, and specificity requirements for the simultaneous determination of Aspirin and Ticlopidine Hydrochloride. Accuracy (recoveries: 99.44 and 99.60%) and reproducibility were found to be satisfactory. The proposed method was found suitable for the routine quality control analysis of the drugs in tablet dosage forms. [43]

Mehul Patel et al

A new UV-Visible spectrophotometry method has been developed to simultaneously estimate the amounts of Aspirin (ASP) and 5-Fluorouracil (5-FU) in their bulk form. This method is simple, sensitive, selective, economical, and reproducible. The absorbance of ASP and 5-FU in 0.1N HCl was measured at 234 nm and 266 nm, respectively. The concentration ranges for ASP and 5-FU were 12-32 µg/mL and 3.33-8.89 µg/mL, respectively, and the correlation coefficients (r) were 0.9971 and 0.9944 for ASP at 234 nm and 266 nm, and 0.9988 and 0.9975 for 5-FU at 266 nm and 234 nm. The limit of detection (LOD) was found to be 0.16 µg/mL for ASP and 0.04 µg/mL for 5-FU, while the limit of quantification (LOQ) was 0.48 µg/mL for ASP and 0.13 µg/mL for 5-FU. The developed method was validated according to the current ICH guidelines, and the precision results (% RSD) for both ASP and 5-FU at 234 nm and 266 nm were below 2%. The accuracy of the method was satisfactory, with % recovery values ranging from 98.00% to 102.38% for ASP and 98.41% to 100.81% for 5-FU. The assay of the dosage form

showed a drug content of 99.57% for ASP and 98.97% for 5-FU. [7]

Shubham D. Chaudhari et al

Developed and validated analytical methods for the simultaneous estimation of rosuvastatin and aspirin dosage in combine dosage form A reliable and accurate UV spectroscopic method has been developed to simultaneously determine the levels of Rosuvastatin and Aspirin in both bulk and capsule forms. The method utilizes the absorbance ratio technique, measuring absorption at wavelengths 239nm and 233nm, corresponding to the maximum absorption for Rosuvastatin and Aspirin, respectively. The range of linearity for Rosuvastatin is found to be between 4 and 14 µg/ml, while for Aspirin it is between 20 and 60 µg/ml. The accuracy of the method falls within the range of 99.62% to 99.73% for both drugs. Validation tests for linearity, accuracy, and precision were conducted, and the method can be applied to pharmaceutical formulations without interference from other substances. The results were validated according to the guidelines set by the International Council for Harmonisation (ICH).[8]

A Raja Reddy et al

In these Aspirin is determined using Spectrophotometrically using FC Reagent An experiment was conducted to develop a new, easy-to-use, and affordable spectrophotometric technique for measuring the concentration of aspirin. The method involved using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent to react with the phenolic groups in aspirin, forming a blue coloured Chromogen. The spectrum analysis showed that the maximum absorbance occurred at 750 nm, and the concentration range of 2-20 µg/ml was found to follow Beer's Law with a correlation coefficient of 0.9997. The accuracy, precision, and robustness of the method were validated, with the precision having a %RSD of 0.94%. The limit of detection and quantification for the method was found to be

0.43 and 1.31 µg/ml, respectively. The results of the proposed method were statistically validated according to ICH Q2 R1 guidelines and were deemed satisfactory.[9]

Emine Akdemir et al

Development and Validation of a Novel Analytical Method for the Determination of Dissolution Rate of Acetylsalicylic Acid in Enteric-Coated Tablet Dosage Form by Liquid Chromatography A validated analytical method was developed for assessing the dissolution rate of acetylsalicylic acid in enteric-coated tablet forms using liquid chromatography. The method utilized reversed-phase liquid chromatography with PDA and TUV detection on a HCLASS-UHPLC system, employing a UHPLC column with dimensions of 2.1mm x 50mm. The mobile phase comprised a solution of heptane-1-sulfonic acid sodium salt in acetonitrile and deionized water (15%:85% v/v), with a flow rate of 0.5ml/min at 25°C. Detection occurred at 280nm, with the method successfully determining salicylic acid as well. Validation studies adhering to ICH Q2(R1) guidelines confirmed specificity, linearity (correlation coefficient > 0.99), system precision (RSD 0.06%-0.12%), repeatability (RSD 1.69%), and intermediate precision (RSD 0.94%). Accuracy and robustness were also within acceptable ranges (96.6%-98.0% for acetylsalicylic acid and 95.6%-98.9% for salicylic acid), establishing the method's reliability for dissolution rate determination in enteric-coated tablets. [10]

Ross D. Kirchhoefer

In these salicylic acid and aspirin concentrations were measured simultaneously in bulk aspirin, buffered, and enteric-coated tablets using high pressure liquid chromatography equipped with UV and fluorescence detectors. A high-pressure liquid chromatographic method employing UV and fluorescence detectors was developed for the simultaneous determination of aspirin and

salicylic acid in bulk aspirin and various tablet formulations, including plain, buffered, and enteric-coated tablets. The procedure demonstrated excellent recovery rates of 100% for both compounds in simulated tablet samples. The analysis, based on UV absorbance at 254 nm for aspirin and fluorescence detection at 425 nm for salicylic acid, exhibited minimal interference from excipients and impurities. Comparison with the USP XIX procedure revealed good agreement, with low coefficients of variation (0.59% for aspirin and 1.69% for salicylic acid). Additionally, the hydrolysis rate of aspirin in the solvents was determined to be negligible. Overall, this novel method offers a reliable and precise approach for the quantification of aspirin and salicylic acid in different tablet formulations.[11]

Keisuke kitamura et al

Determination of Aspirin and Salicylic Acid in Aspirin Tablets by Second Derivative Ultraviolet Spectrometry The second derivative ultraviolet (UV) spectra of aspirin and salicylic acid were not affected by the strong and time-dependent signal backgrounds caused by excipients and antacids present in powdered aspirin tablets. To prevent the promotion of aspirin hydrolysis to salicylic acid by antacids, a solvent consisting of ethanol with 1% (w/v) citric acid was utilized. Three different types of commercially available aspirin tablets were analyzed using second derivative UV spectrometry, without the need for separating the active pharmaceutical ingredients from the tablet additives. The concentrations of aspirin and salicylic acid were determined with relative standard deviations less than 0.5% for aspirin and less than 3.0% for salicylic acid.[13]

Ochieng Anthony et al

A Comparative Analysis of Aspirin from Various Analgesic Formulations Using Titrimetry, Spectroscopic and Hypedated Chromatographic Techniques Aspirin, also known as acetyl salicylic acid or 2-acetoxybenzoic acid, contains a

carboxylic acid functional group, which makes it easy to quantify using a strong alkali like sodium hydroxide (NaOH). However, in tablet formulations containing aspirin along with other acidic excipients or substituents, NaOH is not suitable for quantifying aspirin because these acidic components react with NaOH. The absorbance of each solution was recorded at a wavelength of 297.4 nm, which corresponds to λ_{max} . [14]

Purushotam Sinha et al

A Validated Stability Indicating HPTLC Method for Determination of Aspirin and Clopidogrel Bisulphate in Combined Dosage Form

A reliable method was developed for the analysis of Aspirin and Clopidogrel bisulphate using High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC) according to ICH guidelines. The goal of the method was to accurately determine the compounds' responses without interference from their degradation products. The stationary phase used was TLC aluminium plates coated with silica gel 60 F254. The solvent system comprised of a mixture of carbon tetrachloride and acetone in a ratio of 6:2.4 (v/v). This solvent system produced well-defined spots for both Aspirin and Clopidogrel bisulphate with R_f values of 0.13±0.02 and 0.78±0.02 respectively. To evaluate the stability of the drugs, they were subjected to various stress conditions including acid, alkali, and neutral hydrolysis, oxidation, dry heat treatment, and photodegradation. The resulting degradation products were successfully separated from the drugs' spots. Densitometric analysis of the drugs was performed using absorbance measured at 220 nm. The calibration plots obtained for both Aspirin and Clopidogrel bisulphate exhibited good linearity with correlation coefficients (r^2) of 0.9991 and 0.9866, respectively, within the concentration ranges of 200-600 ng/spot and 300-600 ng/spot. These findings suggest that the drugs

are prone to degradation to varying degrees under different conditions. [12]

Antonino Villari et al

Spectrofluorimetry at zero angle: determination of salicylic acid in an acetylsalicylic acid pharmaceutical formulation

In this study, a new method using solid-state spectrofluorimetric was developed to analyse drugs. Specifically, focused was on detecting salicylic acid (SA) in solid pharmaceutical formulations that also contain acetylsalicylic acid (ASA). The reproducibility of the spectrofluorimetric method, expressed as the relative standard deviation, ranged from 0.1 to 0.3% for both within and between days. For this method, a fluorescence apparatus with in-line excitation and detection systems (zero angle) is required. The detection system was not affected by the excitation wavelength, but it showed high sensitivity to emission wavelengths between 350 and 800 nm. The sensitivity of the developed method was in the range of 10^{-8} grams. [15]

Analytical Methods for Aspirin

- IP-2010 (Aspirin tablet) -Potentiometric Titration- Titrate: Tablet Powder Equivalent to 0.5 gm. Aspirin in 30ml of the 0.5M Sodium Hydroxide Titrant:-0.5 M HCl 1ml of 0.5M NaOH is Equivalent to .0.04504 gm. of Aspirin [17]
- BP-2009- Potentiometric Titration - Titrate: 1gm Aspirin in 10ml Ethanol, Add 50ml of the 0.5M Sodium Hydroxide Titrant: 0.5 M HCl 1ml of 0.5M NaOH is Equivalent to .0.04504 gm. of Aspirin [18]
- USP30-NF25 (Aspirin Tablet) - Liquid Chromatography - Mobile phase: Water (pH 3.4): Acetonitrile (85:15) Column: Packing L1, (300 mm × 4.0 mm) Flow rate: 2 ml/min Wavelength: 285 nm. [19]

Reported Methods for Aspirin

1. The mobile phase, which is composed of 2.5 pH sodium perchlorate buffer, 85:14:1

acetonitrile, and isopropyl alcohol, is essential to the separation process. A C18 column of 100 mm by 4.6 mm and containing particles with a size of 5 μ is used in the stationary phase. A reversed-phase column with an octadecyl functional group is indicated by the selection of C18. The flow rate, which controls how quickly the mobile phase moves through the system, is fixed at 1.5 ml/min. A wavelength of 275 nm is used for detection, signifying the absorption of ultraviolet light during examination. This thorough HPLC technique offers a reliable and focused way for measuring aspirin in samples, which is essential for analytical and medicinal applications.[20]

2. A particular chromatographic technique has been described for the RP-HPLC analysis of aspirin and metoprolol. In the mobile phase, methanol and phosphate buffer (pH 4.6) are combined in a 20:80 ratio. The separation of aspirin and metoprolol during the chromatographic process depends on this combination. This indicates the usage of a reversed-phase column with octadecyl functional groups. The stationary phase uses a Phenomenex Luna C18 column with dimensions of 250 mm $\times$ 4.6 mm and a particle size of 5 μ . The flow rate, which controls how quickly the mobile phase moves through the system, is set at 0.8 ml/min. At 230 nm, detection is carried out, signifying the analysis's absorption of ultraviolet light. [21]
3. A unique chromatographic method has been created for the simultaneous determination of Aspirin, Ramipril, Hydrochlorothiazide, Simvastatin, and Atenolol in the context of RP-HPLC analysis. The mobile phase is a 95:5 mixture of methanol and water that acts as an essential solvent system for the pharmaceutical chemicals that need to be separated. The stationary phase uses a 250 mm $\times$ 4.6 mm Hypersil Gold C18 column with a 5 μ particle size, demonstrating the use of a reversed-phase column containing an octadecyl functional group. The mobile phase moves through the system at a specific pace, which is determined by setting the flow rate at 1 ml/min. A wavelength of 230 nm is used for detection, denoting the absorption of UV light during examination. [22]
4. The RP-HPLC technique calls for a certain chromatographic configuration in order to analyze aspirin and prasugrel at the same time. The mobile phase, which is a crucial solvent system for the separation of the two medicinal substances, is made up of acetonitrile and acetate buffer in a 75:25 ratio. A 150 mm $\times$ 4.6 mm Luna C18 column with a 5 μ particle size facilitates the chromatographic separation, demonstrating the usage of an octadecyl functional group reversed-phase column. The flow rate is kept constant at 0.6 ml/min, which controls how quickly the mobile phase passes through the system. In order to emphasize the absorption of UV light during analysis, detection is carried out at a wavelength of 245 nm.[23]
5. The stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for Aspirin and Prasugrel analysis employs a mobile phase of Acetonitrile, Methanol, and Water (pH 3, 30:10:60) for efficient separation. Utilizing a Kromasil-100 C18 column (150 mm $\times$ 4.6 mm, 5 μ) with a flow rate of 1 ml/min, the method allows for precise quantification. Detection at 245 nm ensures sensitivity to UV absorption. This approach is specifically designed to assess the stability of Aspirin and Prasugrel, making it a valuable tool in pharmaceutical quality control and formulation studies.[24]
6. Acetonitrile and 0.05% Trifluoroacetic Acid are combined in a 30:70 ratio to form the mobile phase used in the RP-HPLC technique

for the simultaneous measurement of salicylic acid and aspirin. A Waters C18 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μ) is used to achieve separation; this indicates a reversed-phase column containing functional groups of octadecyl. The speed of the mobile phase is determined by setting the flow rate at 1.0 ml/min. To ensure sensitivity to ultraviolet absorption, detection is carried out at a wavelength of 230 nm. For the simultaneous measurement of aspirin and salicylic acid, this HPLC technique provides an effective and accurate method that is useful for pharmaceutical analysis and quality control.[25]

7. A mobile phase consisting of methanol and phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) in a 70:30 ratio is used in the RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous analysis of amlodipine besylate, atenolol, and aspirin. On a BDS C18 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μ), separation is accomplished at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. Sensitivity to UV absorption is guaranteed by the 235 nm detection wavelength. This technique is useful in analytical and pharmaceutical applications because it provides an effective and accurate way to quantify the three medicinal components simultaneously.[26]
8. The RP-HPLC method uses a particular chromatographic configuration to analyze aspirin and its derivatives. Acetonitrile and water are combined in the mobile phase at a 60:40 ratio for optimal compound separation. Utilizing a 180 mm × 4.6 mm Kromasil C18 column with a 5 μ particle size and reversed-phase characteristics (i.e., an octadecyl functional group), chromatographic separation is accomplished. The mobile phase moves through the system at a set speed, determined by the flow rate, which is kept at 1.0 ml/min. The wavelength at which the detection is carried out, 277 nm, guarantees sensitivity to the absorption of ultraviolet radiation. This HPLC method is essential for analytical and pharmaceutical applications because it offers a methodical and trustworthy way to simultaneously measure aspirin and its derivatives.[27]
9. The RP-HPLC method makes use of a particular chromatographic configuration for the simultaneous analysis of aspirin, caffeine, and orphenadrine citrate. In order to enable efficient compound separation, the mobile phase is composed of 65:35 methanol and pH 3 phosphate buffer. A reversed-phase column containing an octadecyl functional group, the Acclaim C18 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μ) is used to produce chromatographic separation. The mobile phase's velocity through the system is established by maintaining the flow rate at 1.0 ml/min. In order to ensure sensitivity to UV light absorption, detection is carried out at a wavelength of 215 nm. For the purpose of simultaneously measuring aspirin, caffeine, and orphenadrine citrate, this HPLC method provides an accurate and effective method that is useful in analytical and medicinal applications.[28]
10. Aspirin and dipyridamole are analyzed together using the RP-HPLC method, which uses a particular chromatographic configuration. Effective compound separation is facilitated by the 75:25 ratio of 0.1% phosphoric acid to acetonitrile in the mobile phase. A reversed-phase column having an octadecyl functional group, the RP C18 column (50 mm × 4.6 mm, 3.5 μ) is used to produce chromatographic separation. The mobile phase's velocity through the system is established by maintaining the flow rate at 1.0 ml/min. In order to ensure sensitivity to UV light absorption, detection is carried out at a

wavelength of 227 nm. With its accurate and effective method for simultaneously measuring aspirin and dipyridamole, this HPLC technique is useful for analytical and medicinal applications.[29]

11. Using a particular chromatographic configuration, the RP-HPLC technique analyzes aspirin and esomeprazole magnesium simultaneously. To enable the efficient separation of the two chemicals, the mobile phase is composed of acetonitrile, methanol, and phosphate buffer in a 25:25:50 ratio at a pH of 3.0. ODS BP C18 (200 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μ) reversed-phase column containing octadecyl functional group is used to produce chromatographic separation. The rate at which the mobile phase passes through the system is selected, and it is fixed at 1.0 ml/min. This ensures sensitivity to absorption of UV light, with detection occurring at a wavelength of 230 nm.[30]
12. The RP-HPLC method uses a particular chromatographic configuration in order to analyze Simvastatin, Aspirin, and Ramipril simultaneously. Acetonitrile, methanol, and 0.5% phosphoric acid are combined in the mobile phase in the ratio 10:70:20 to enable efficient separation of the three substances. Utilizing an ODS BP C18 column (200 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μ), which indicates a reversed-phase column with an octadecyl functional group, chromatographic separation is accomplished. The speed of the mobile phase through the system is determined by maintaining the flow rate at 1.0 ml/min. The wavelength at which the detection is performed, 226 nm, guarantees sensitivity to the absorption of ultraviolet radiation.[31]
13. The RP-HPLC technique uses a particular chromatographic configuration to analyze aspirin, salicylic acid, and caffeine simultaneously. In order to enable efficient compound separation, the mobile phase is composed of water, methanol, and acetic acid in the ratio 69:28:3. This method provides an accurate and effective solution for concurrent quantification, useful in pharmaceutical and analytical applications. It uses a Hypersil C18 column (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μ) with a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min and detection at 275 nm.[32]
14. In the RP-HPLC method for simultaneous analysis of Aspirin and Clopidogrel, a specific chromatographic setup is employed. The mobile phase comprises 3% o-Phosphoric acid and Acetonitrile in a ratio of 65:35, facilitating effective compound separation on a Phenomenex C18 column (25 cm X 4.6 mm, 5 μ m). With a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min and detection at 266 nm, this method offers a precise and efficient approach for concurrent quantification, essential in pharmaceutical and analytical applications.[33]
15. A particular chromatographic configuration is needed for the RP-HPLC method to analyze aspirin and clopidogrel bisulphate simultaneously. To effectively separate compounds on a C18 column (25 cm X 4.6 mm, 5 μ m), the mobile phase is composed of acetonitrile, phosphate buffer with pH 3.0, and methanol in a ratio of 50:30:20. This technology, which has a detection wavelength of 240 nm and a flow rate of 1.5 ml/min, provides an accurate and effective means of concurrent quantification, which is crucial for analytical and pharmaceutical applications.[34]
16. The stability-indicating RP-HPLC approach for clopidogrel and aspirin uses a specific chromatographic setup. On a Phenyl Hexyl column (25 cm X 4.6 mm, 5 μ m), the mobile phase comprises Solvent A (Phosphate Buffer, pH 2.3) and Solvent B (Methanol: Acetonitrile, 50:50), which enable efficient

compound separation. This technique offers an accurate and effective way to measure aspirin and clopidogrel while evaluating stability, which is important in pharmaceutical and analytical applications. It has a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min and detects at 220 nm.[35]

17. Ion Pair RP-HPLC for Aspirin and Clopidogrel Bisulphate analysis uses a specific chromatographic methodology. Acetonitrile and Tetrabutylammonium Hydrogen Sulphate Buffer are combined in a 50:50 ratio to form the mobile phase, which allows for efficient compound separation on a Lichrosphere-100 column (25 cm X 4.6 mm, 5 µm). This approach provides accurate simultaneous quantification of Clopidogrel and Aspirin at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min and a detection wavelength of 240 nm. It is especially well-suited for ion-pair chromatography applications.[36]

18. A particular chromatographic arrangement is used in the RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous measurement of aspirin, atorvastatin calcium, and clopidogrel bisulphate. Utilizing an Inertsil ODS column (15 cm X 4.6 mm, 5 µm) with acetonitrile and phosphate buffer in a 50:50 ratio at pH 3.0, the mobile phase allows for efficient compound separation. This method enables accurate and effective quantification of the three chemicals, which is important in pharmaceutical and analytical applications. It has a flow rate of 1.2 ml/min and detects at 235 nm.[37]

19. The RP-HPLC method for simultaneous analysis of Aspirin, Atorvastatin Calcium, and Clopidogrel Bisulphate utilizes a precise chromatographic setup. The mobile phase, comprising Acetonitrile, Water with pH 3.0, and Methanol in a ratio of 50:40:10, enables effective compound separation on a Hypersil BDS C18 column (25 cm X 4.6 mm, 5 µm). With a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min and detection

at 248 nm, this method provides accurate and efficient quantification of the three compounds, integral in pharmaceutical and analytical contexts.[38]

20. A specific chromatographic configuration is used in the RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous analysis of Rosuvastatin and Aspirin. Effective compound separation on an X-Terra C18 column (15 cm X 4.6 mm, 5 µm) is made possible by the mobile phase, which is made up of methanol and buffer at a 45:55 ratio. This approach offers accurate and effective quantification of both substances, which is crucial in pharmaceutical and analytical applications, with a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min and detection at 215 nm.[39]

21. In RP-HPLC analysis for Aspirin and Rosuvastatin Calcium, a specific chromatographic method is applied. The mobile phase, consisting of Water with 0.5% Triethylamine and Acetonitrile in a 50:50 ratio, facilitates effective separation on a Smart C18 column (25 cm X 4.6 mm, 5 µm). With a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min and detection at 243 nm, this method ensures precise and efficient quantification of both compounds, crucial for pharmaceutical and analytical applications.[40]

22. A specific chromatographic method is used in the RP-HPLC analysis for aspirin and rosuvastatin calcium. Effective compound separation on a Hyperchrome ODS BP column (20 cm X 4.6 mm, 5 µm) is facilitated by the mobile phase, which consists of acetonitrile in a 45:55 ratio and phosphate buffer with a pH of 3.0. This approach provides accurate and effective results using a 1.0 ml/min flow rate and 241 nm detection. [41]

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